

Abstract

Effect of an Acupuncture Treatment Protocol on the Patellar Reflex in Parkinson's Disease Patients – Case Series Study.

Catarina Ramos Pereira^{1,2,3,4*} , Bruno Ramos^{1,3}, Maria João Santos^{2,4}, and Henry Johannes Greten^{8,9}.

¹ ICBAS - School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Portugal;

² Piaget Institute, Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal;

³ CBSIn - Centre of Biosciences in Integrative Health, Porto, Portugal;

⁴ Academia de Saúde C+, Porto, Portugal;

⁵ 1H-TOXRUN - Toxicology Research Unit, CESPU - University Institute of Health Sciences, Gandra, Paredes, Portugal;

⁶ ESS – School of Health, Polytechnic of Porto, Porto, Portugal;

⁷ Pedro Hispano Hospital, Matosinhos, Portugal;

⁸ DGTCM - German Society of Traditional Chinese Medicine, Heidelberg, Germany;

⁹ HSCM - Heidelberg School of Chinese Medicine, Heidelberg, Germany.

* Correspondence: catarinapereira.mtc@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction: The investigation of rigidity physiology in Parkinson's Disease involves the examination of reflexes. Parkinsonian patients often demonstrate reduced sensitivity in polysynaptic reflexes within the leg extensor muscles, which is correlated with their postural instability. The compensatory mechanisms for impaired proprioceptive reflex function may involve alterations in intrinsic muscle stiffness. The interplay between gait and reflexes is intricately linked to the nervous system's functioning and motor control. Certain reflexes, such as the patellar reflex, play a pivotal role in maintaining walking and posture. Ensuring the integrity of these reflexes is essential for facilitating smooth and efficient walking. **Aim:** To analyse the behaviour of the patellar reflex in four Parkinson's Disease patients undergoing an acupuncture treatment protocol. **Methods:** This study adopts a case series design. Reflex outcomes based on amplitude and velocity were assessed at six different time moments throughout a month-long treatment protocol using the MP 36, Biopac Systems. **Results:** Over the long term, a tendency for an improvement in range of movement and velocity of the patellar reflex was observed. Nevertheless, in specific cases, a reduction in the amplitude during acute effects was also found. **Conclusion:** Our findings suggest that the acupuncture protocol used may lead to a cumulative improvement in the efficacy of the patellar reflex in patients with Parkinson's disease. However, further in-depth research, including a statistical evaluation with a larger participant pool, is necessary to validate and confirm these promising preliminary results.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Heidelberg Model; Parkinson's Disease; Patellar Reflex; Biopac System; Amplitude.

Citation: Pereira C.R., Machado J., Criado B., Santos R., Reis A.M., Ramos B., Santos M.J., Greten H.J. Effect of an Acupuncture Treatment Protocol on the Patellar Reflex in Parkinson's Disease Patients – Case Series Study. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(2) 10.5281/zenodo.16812197

Received: 24 March 2025

Accepted: 28 March 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral concerning jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 2nd International Congress on Complementary Therapies in Health, held on 28 June 2025. The full-text article was published as Pereira C.R., Machado J., Criado B., Santos R., Reis A.M., Ramos B., Santos M.J., Greten H.J. Analysis of patellar reflex in Parkinson disease patients after an acupuncture treatment protocol – Case series study. *Clinical Parkinsonism & Related Disorders*. 2025;12,100324 [10.1016/j.prdoa.2025.100324](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prdoa.2025.100324).